

A Study on the Effectiveness of Infographics in HEI Websites with Special Reference to Coimbatore City

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Abstract: Infographics are quickly emerging as a useful way to convey information succinctly in a world where people struggle with too much information. Despite infographics' ongoing growth, little study has been done to show how educators may use this new resource. The effectiveness of infographics resides in their ability to swiftly and effectively convey vast volumes of data. This paper defines the criteria for infographics to have a potential role on educational websites. This research paper mainly focused the process of use of digital media and specifically what the role in decision-making process of choosing a college. This knowledge of the use of digital marketing in higher education institutions (HEI) especially as part of the colleges' strategy is very crucial to compete for qualified students. The paper aims to demonstrate the role and application of infographics a digital marketing tool to help student's decision-making process. A qualitative research approach was employed in this study through semi-structured interviews, observation and documentation as data collection method. Chi-square analysis were done in this research study as part of analysis.

The collaborative and engaging nature of websites provides an opportunity to balance the educational control since communication platform is built on opinions and experiences of students and other stakeholders.

Keywords : Infographics, Digital marketing ,HEI Websites ,Students decisions
JEL Classification Number : I23,M31,Z0

1.Introduction

The Internet's vast access to a wide range of information resources provides users with a distinct advantage in quickly obtaining the knowledge they seek across various sectors. In the early stages of the Internet's development, information was primarily delivered in textual form due to the limitations imposed by the software and hardware environment. However, with the advancements in information and communication technologies, as well as computer hardware, graphic and multimedia content can now be extensively utilized. Humans naturally gravitate towards visual experiences, and the inclusion of high-clarity multimedia

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Mark Anthony Camilleri (2020) describes his paper as global marketing environment of today's higher education. Today's educational institutions are acting more like for-profit businesses and looking for new chances to generate income. To promote their global market, they currently focus on modern integrated marketing communication. Consequently, it's a hard socioeconomic climate on this competitive planet. The widespread usage of interactive digital education systems at the current stage of technological advancement in education allows students to make decisions with a high degree of independence because they are managed based on a variety of scenarios. The development of adaptive management solutions for digital education is currently receiving a lot of attention. They enable the schooling process to be very effective.

This study suggests that students in the "digital age" necessitate a form of learning that aligns with the digital environment, involving visual representations of data to capture and maintain their attention. Marabella, (2014). According to Barnard, (1921), 'a picture can express a thousand words. People frequently skim and check for headlines or images that grab their attention. As a result of monitoring and scanning for headlines, crucial information may be quickly discarded, lost, or ignored. This story-telling technique will grab attention before something else does and has a name: infographics. Infographics are graphical and visual representations of information, data, or knowledge that can be used to rapidly and effectively comprehend, translate, and integrate challenging material Newsom & Haynes, (2004); Smiciklas, (2012). By enhancing the ability of the human visual system to recognize patterns and trends through the use of visuals, infographics increase user comprehension Card, (2009).

Pictures combined with minimal text remove the barriers that make comprehensive easy. Information graphic is referred to as an infographic.

Visualization is the process of utilizing graphics to swiftly and convey data or information

Nan & Dur, (2012). In the worlds of business, social media, and design, infographics have emerged as a simple method for disseminating useful information to an audience.

Why we need infographics means it can help people understand complex concepts by using visual aids such as charts, graphs, and diagrams. They can use both images and text in a visual format to explain concepts. They are often used for marketing purposes but they can be useful when writing articles or sharing research, and it is more effective because they combine the written word with visual elements to park big ideas into small spaces. Presenting information in such a compelling fashion encourages visitors to spend time on your sites, consuming and sharing more of your content.

Technological developments have changed the use of web-based environments and the understanding of sharing through these environments. In particular, Web 2.0 technologies and the changes in content development approaches enabled users to produce web contents Karaman, Yildirim and Kaban, (2008). Thus, users of web-based environments have also gained the identity of the person producing the data in these environments Atici and Yildirim, (2010). Including web technologies and new environments in the process has contributed many changes in the education.

Effective design of educational websites is important for web users .As a promotional medium, changes to the web can be quickly implemented and with limited cost. Websites that are dynamic are those that get the hits. The Web enables the display of photos, sound, and short movie clips at lower costs. Frequently Asked Questions on websites can address typical admission questions from customers, freeing up a lot of time for office staff. Websites serve customers 24 hours a day, seven days a week, without additional costs. Websites can efficiently reach target customers by presenting the right branding message at the right time, at the right place, to the right person - for optimum results Belch & Belch, (2007); Chaffey et al., (2006); et al., (2007); Strauss et al., (2006).

Comparing the Web to other mediums such as print media advertising, education fairs, exhibitions, personnel fees, information sessions and publication mails, a website is cheaper, with faster and wider audience coverage Belch & Belch, (2007); Chaffey et al., (2006); et al., (2007); Strauss et al., (2006). This is in line with the quote, "Marketing on the Internet has received substantial attention. Businesses are not only able to reach a wider audience but also reduce marketing costs" Ellsworth & Ellsworth, (1994).

As indicated by Porter (2001), "The Internet is a powerful set of tools that can be used, wisely or unwisely, in almost every industry and as part of almost any strategy". He stressed that companies that succeed will be the ones that use the Internet as complementary to traditional ways of competing, not those that set their Internet initiatives apart from their

established operations Porter, (2001).

In summary, although there are many advantages of having websites, Higher education institutions providers need to consider and overcome some common mistakes and limitations of websites. This is to ensure the institution's website is a marketing tool and brings value the institution.

Emerging digital technology-based environments have significantly contributed to enriching educational purposes with different features and formats, thus allowing information transfer to learners in various methods and techniques. In particular, infographics technology is, indeed, one of the most prominent information presentation tools as it empowers users to display required information in an organized way as well as its delivery using different visual stimuli. Information graphics, or infographics, combine elements of data visualization with design and have become an increasingly popular means for disseminating data. While several studies have suggested that aesthetics in visualization and infographics relate to desirable outcomes like engagement and memorability, it remains unknown how quickly aesthetic impressions are formed, and what it is that makes an infographic appealing. Complex graphic and multimedia information inevitably leads to the need to change the paradigm of the educational process organization. It can be argued, that the era of multimedia content dominance has inevitably come, and this trend will only increase in the near future.

2. Statement of the problem

General, the majority of the websites at different colleges all over the world are still persistent in relying on using a traditional way of huge text, characters, and variables to present a piece of information. As a result, the researcher personally realized that fact, if new emerging digital technologies and tools like infographics (information graphics) are utilized in the presentation of data, it will be possible to overcome the chronic problem of providing students with a huge amount of information .instead such information can be presented in an attractive visual form making it easy for students.

The researcher observed the unwillingness to read and understand the huge text on the website for the students, informally considerable meetings were conducted with college students providing them with the same information presented in both conventional and visual infographics versions. Overall 80% of the students confirmed that technologically presented information was better easier to remember, summarize, and more comprehensible.

2.1 Research questions

1. Can we create infographics for educational institutions?

2. To determine the impact of the infographics website on attracting students?

3. Objectives

Interpret the infographic contents help the students to make better decisions.
To assess the significance of infographics in websites on attracting students.
To analyse the importance of infographics on HEI websites

4. Conceptual framework

Study -1

Study -2

Limitations

- This study measured the perception of students in the field of MBA.it is recommended that similar studies be conducted with students in another field of study.
- Future research may also want to focus on segmenting the market base and also with other information sources than websites
- Designers should pay attention to the consistency of content of information, taxonomic level and layout that are provided by visualization
- The study which is limited to 3 to 4 College websites at Coimbatore city
- Website creation, database collection, and adding features and new technology make a dynamic website more difficult job.

- There are numerous factors that make up an education website, but in this paper, the researcher only uses four of them for the study.
- When researching theoretical concepts possible misinterpretation from the research part is always a present risk.
- The researcher encountered some challenges when gathering data from students because they were unfamiliar with the subject.

6. Literature review

6.1 Introduction

Many previous kinds of research tried to discuss and show the effect of Digital Marketing in different institutions and environments. Some of their research results show that E-Marketing can have a significant influence on achieving customer satisfaction (Abo-Qaood & Al- Dhaimat, 2016). In addition, it is possible to measure students' acceptance of modern technology in education which reflects the ability and readiness of students to deal with this technological development. Accordingly, many colleges do not show privacy notices on how the institutions use the personal information collected on their websites and the quality of web design and services has an impact on attracting users to use websites. Studies have shown that the attractiveness of website design and the integrated services increases the user's interaction and satisfaction with the quality of the website because it meets all their needs (Hasan & Abuelrub, 2011).

This research focuses on the literature review in infographics, infographics in education, and infographics design. The result of the research revealed that using and creating infographics will develop visual literacy skills, which will help the students to make sense of and evaluate information. The infographics creators should consider the foremost structure, accuracy, reliability, depth, and functionality and then think about duration. Infographics need analysing, evaluation, and creation. several studies of infographics that have been done by previous researchers dealing with the use of infographics, in education, and designing infographics.

Why infographics? Why visual information is a more effective form of communication for humans? – the science of infographics krum, (2014).

1. Vision is the strongest form of input that we use to perceive the world around us. A Vision is by far our most dominant sense, taking up half of our brain's resources. b. Studies estimate that between 50-80 percent of the human brain is dedicated to forms of visual processing, such as vision, visual memory, colors, shapes, movement, patterns, spatial awareness and image recollection.

2. A simple text message combined with a relevant image can make a lasting, memorable impression on your audience. a. When we read the text alone, we are likely to remember only 10 percent of the information 3 days later. b. If that information is presented to use as text combined with a relevant image, we are likely to remember 65 percent of the information 3 days later.

3. Data visualization leverages humans' pattern recognition abilities and significantly accelerates the understanding of the data.

6.2 C. F. Provvidenza, L. R. Hartman, J. Carmichael, and N. Reed (2019), researcher posits that the utilization of infographics holds promise as a strategic approach for facilitating the transfer of information to diverse audiences, as evidenced in this article. The concept of knowledge translation (KT) encapsulates the frequency with which such infographics-based content is employed to swiftly convey information. Multiple stakeholders leverage infographics with the primary intentions.

6.3 A. Taspolat, O. S. Kaya, H. F. Sapanca, M. Beheshti, and F. Ozdamli (2017), the current digital era, the significance of infographics cannot be overstated. This research article endeavors to elucidate the advantages, fundamental principles, and design methodologies underlying infographics, aligning them with the prevailing educational trends.

6.4 S. P. John and R. De'Villiers, (2020), plays a pivotal role in the realm of promotion and marketing, particularly in the context of educational tourism destinations. This study aims to investigate the influence of visual media on the perceptions of potential audiences towards specific educational tourism destinations and how it aids marketers in shaping consumer decisions. The findings of this study offer valuable insights to tertiary education agents engaged in promoting international studies, destination marketers, and other users of visual media as communicators.

6.5 M. Nowakowski, (2020), study focuses on analyzing and evaluating the utility of information and user experience when presented in textual and graphic formats on consumer behavior and decision-making within internet services. Through the examination of various forms of information and data analysis involving a group of respondents, this paper aims to provide valuable insights for creating assumptions about effective content presentation and visualization methods for information and business websites. Ultimately, the findings of this study can contribute to enhancing the design and presentation of content to better serve the needs of users in online contexts.

6.6 A. Kusumawati, (2019), says in today's competitive landscape, it has become increasingly crucial for universities to differentiate themselves and successfully promote their offerings to prospective students. Recognizing the significance of digital media as a commercial platform, universities are progressively embracing online marketing channels over traditional methods. This research paper aims to investigate the intricate process through which students utilize digital media and, more specifically, the role it plays in their

decision-making process when selecting a university. Understanding the utilization of digital marketing within Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), particularly as a component of university marketing strategies, is paramount in order to effectively compete for qualified students.

6.7 Vasiljeva,(2017), studied digital marketing, online marketing, or web marketing has emerged as a prominent and highly relevant research topic, particularly within the realm of higher educational institutions. The author emphasizes the significance of employing diverse tools in web marketing to engage customers, capture their attention, and facilitate effective online communication with the younger generation. The exploration of these aspects holds substantial importance in understanding how educational institutions can leverage digital marketing strategies to successfully engage and connect with their target audience

6.8 Kelidou and K. Siountri (2020), provided a thorough explanation of this subject. He mostly discussed the tool's entire concept, emphasising how effective it is for visual data presenting. Basic concepts from complex data. As a result, research is still being done on this area. This paper seeks to distinguish between the benefits of infographics and their drawbacks.

6.9 M. Ranjbarfard and M. Kheiri, (2019), researcher discovered infographics' function on websites. Most websites today measure themselves in new, dynamic ways. Therefore, we ought to make our websites more entertaining and educational. Today's consumers expect more information faster and are not at all interested in static websites. He used a sample of 311 people for the survey, the majority of whom were selected using partial least squares methods (PLS)

6.10 H. Naparin and A. Binti Saad, (2017), paper centers around the examination of infographics in the realm of education. Infographics are highly regarded as a powerful tool for presenting data in a compelling and impactful manner. In contrast to the conventional methods of knowledge transfer employed by educational institutions, recent advancements have introduced more effective tools for conveying information in a simplified and accessible manner. The primary focus of this essay is to delve into the utilization of infographics in diverse forms of teaching, highlighting their potential benefits and contributions to the educational process

6.11 K. Kalia and N. Goswami, (2021), adapted digital technology in the contemporary period of education is discussed by the researcher in this research piece. For research, the author employed analytical and secondary data. According to his research, new technologies in education are very practical and efficient.

6.12 H. A. Ahmad Hassan AL-NAZER, N. Abdel Aziz SALEH, and A. OSAMA, (2020), concentrated on how important it is to use infographics to draw visitors to websites. When compared to text and mentioned in articles, visual communication utilising graphics is one of the most effective methods. For example, websites with visual communication saw a 12% increase in traffic. Other statistical tools could occupy the customers and make them bored.

6.13 R. Ghode, (2013), used infographics to represent data in newspapers mostly concentrated on data that may be displayed in different charts, diagrams, graphs, tables, etc. The e-newspaper was also the focus of the research, how they are utilise various experiments and startegies to continue to expand. In order to provide useful information quickly, the new media channels have focused significantly more on this type of infographic. This study investigates a number of factors, including importance, visual design, instructional style, space, and section designated for infographic use.

6.14 Pivovarov (2016), author points out a new function for social media in academia. This study helps us identify the students' professional competencies that need the most improvement. In addition, social media can be a successful platform for role playing in a classroom setting.

6.15 S. P. John and R. De'Villiers, (2020), study focuses on the important role that social media plays in marketing and promoting a variety of international tourism services. It uses a theoretical framework to investigate how visual media may affect how a potential audience perceives a particular destination for education tourism. This study offers information to higher education professionals who advocate for foreign studies, destination marketers, and other visual media communicators.

7. Research methodology

The study's goal is to determine how various elements of infographics affect websites of higher educational institutions in Coimbatore city. An organized questionnaire was used to gather the data. Within the framework of a mixed-approaches research strategy, including quantitative and qualitative data collection methods, the data were gathered using a structured questionnaire. This method enables a thorough comprehension of the link between infographics' constituent parts and their influence on the websites of higher education institutions in Coimbatore. While the qualitative data will offer deeper insights into users' perspectives, preferences, and experiences connected to these aspects, the quantitative data gathered through the questionnaire will offer statistical insights into the prevalence and significance of certain infographic elements. The study attempts to provide a comprehensive understanding of how various infographics components affect the efficiency and user experience of websites by utilising a research approach that includes both quantitative and qualitative methods.

7.1 Sources of data

Data collection the main source of information for this study is based on the data collection. Data collected are both primary and secondary in nature.

Primary data

Primary data have been directly collected from the customers by survey method through

undisguised structured questionnaire. Questions like open ended, close ended, multiple choice have been used for the purpose of data collection.

Secondary data

Secondary data have been collected from website and from other Magazines.

7.1 Tool for data collection

The main source of data collection is questionnaire and personal interview. Questionnaire consist of open ended, closed ended, multiple grid, linear grid, check boxes options were in the study.

8. Analysis and interpretation

8.1 Chi –square analysis (X²)

Chi square is a statistical hypothesis test under in the analysis of contingency tables when sample sizes are large .in simple terms ,this test is primarily used to examine whether two categorical variable are independent in influencing the test statistics. The purpose of the test is to determine if a difference between observed data and expected data is due to chance, or if it is due to a relationship between the variables you are studying.

The basic idea behind the test is to compare the observed values in the data to the expected values that will determine the null hypothesis is true. Test returns the probability that a value calculated by the formula could have happened by chance under the assumption of independence.

Formula - $X^2 = \sum (O - E)^2 / E$

O = Observed Frequency 1

E= Expected frequency 2

*E = (Row Total * column Total) / Grand total* 3

*Degree of freedom = (r -1) *(c-1)* 4

8.2 Null and alternative hypothesis

The alternative hypothesis of a test expresses your research's prediction of an effect or relationship, whereas the null hypothesis of a test always predicts no effect or no association between variables.

(H₀) Null hypothesis: There is no significant relationship between the presence of

infographics on college websites and students overall satisfaction of particular websites.

(H1)Alternative hypothesis: There is a significant relationship between the presence of infographics on college websites and students overall satisfaction of particular websites

Table of observed value

Table 1: infographics on college websites and their overall satisfaction

Infographics	Overall satisfaction your website					Total
	1	2	3	4	5	
Yes	0	4	16	12	20	52
No	0	4	7	8	5	24
May be	0	3	8	11	12	34
Total	0	11	31	31	37	110

Table of Expected value

Table 2: Infographics on college websites and their overall satisfaction

Infographics	Overall satisfaction your website					Total
Yes	0	5.2	14.65	14.65	17.49	52
No	0	2.4	6.76	6.76	8.07	24
May be	0	3.4	9.58	9.58	11.43	34

Calculation of x^2

Table 3: infographics on college websites and their overall satisfaction

O	E	(o-E)	(o-E) ²	(o-E) ² /2
0	0	0	0	0
4	5.2	1.2	1.44	0.27
16	14.65	1.35	1.82	0.12
12	14.65	2.65	7.02	0.47
20	17.49	2.51	6.30	0.36
0	0	0	0	0
4	2.4	1.6	2.56	1.06
7	6.76	0.24	0.05	7.39
8	6.76	1.24	1.53	0.22
5	8.07	3.07	9.42	1.16
0	0	0	0	0
3	3.4	0.4	0.16	0.04
8	9.58	1.58	2.49	0.25
11	9.58	1.42	2.01	0.20

12	11.43	0.57	0.32	0.02
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=11.54

Degree of freedom = (column -1) (Row -1)
 (5-1) (3 – 1)
 4 * 2
 = 8

Level of significance = 0.05

Table Value at 0.05 Level of Significance and Degree of Freedom =8

8 =(15.507) Table value

Since the Calculated value is lower than the table value. Hence we fail to reject the null hypothesis.

Results :(Ho) Null hypothesis: There is no significant relationship between the presence of infographics on college websites and students overall satisfaction of particular website

9.Findings

- Out of Total 123 respondents 110 has taken for the analysis. From that 110, 95% of the students are MBA graduates .majority of them claimed that their college have website. The main aim is to make a study on role of infographics in higher educational institutions websites.
- The result was fail to reject the null hypothesis, which is there is no relationship between the infographics contents on websites and satisfaction level of the students.
- The results shows that this kind of new emerging tools are very useful to make the website more attractive and trendy. This kind of system were accepted by the students and they are satisfied and they can move forward confidently by using this infographics tool.
- The present paper is a timely and useful report that can be used to identify the benefits of higher education service provider’s websites to potential students. It can also use to build competitive advantage
- As a promotion medium, changes to the website can be quickly implemented and with limited cost, for that this kind infographics content plays a vital role.
- Infographics is a representation of visual data without additional cost it can efficiently reach target customers by presenting the right brand.
- This study found several useful recommendation for educational institutions to integrate in the improvement of website contents and appearance.

- 71.1% of the students are depend on the information carrying images like infographics more, than they read plain text
- Study finds that these information should be shown as infographics in websites 50% of the students preferred the infrastructure, 22% placement offers details, 28 % cultural programmes and events.

10.Suggestions

- The websites of several colleges were found to be less interactive and cluttered. This could be improved to increase user interface
- Training regarding the several advantages of using infographics could be given to website handlers.
- College websites could become more attractive through GIFs and other multimedia inserts.
- Since infographics act as a visual medium, achievements of the colleges and other positive aspects could be highlighted.
- Student's needs and expectations needs to be researched further, to design future websites.
- Ease of Access is also a factor that greatly affects, how often a student's visits a website.
- User Interface and web design can be simplified to increase it.
- Infographics can summarise page long data into a simple, understandable representation. Visual Aids have always been a better way to pass relevant information, wise usage can capture more attention.
- The websites can follow a theme or a colour palette that runs through the elements in the website. This can improve the overall experience and make the website easily identifiable.
- The Null Hypothesis suggests that websites need to use more infographics to increase student satisfaction.
- College websites are aimed at potential students as well as existing students. The infographics should be clearly placed to fulfil both their needs.
- Infographics is an excellent promotional aid. The colleges can use it promote their achievements and their infrastructure.

Conclusion

This study examines the standards for judging the effectiveness of infographics on the websites of higher education institutions. Websites that are well-designed are advantageous to all prospective and existing students. Since users often want them attractive and to get information quickly, effective web design is crucial for such websites. This serves as the study's context. This survey mostly included MBA graduates to determine the effectiveness

of their college websites and their level of satisfaction with them.

Education institutions should take note of technological advancements which keeps students connected. Given that it adheres to the habits of the present generation, which are changing rapidly along with technology, infographic has become an essential elements on websites. These content offer inexpensive communication and appeal to a wide range of audiences. According to the findings in this area, websites make it simpler to distribute and acquire information. Additionally to being more effective and efficient with the tools offered, such as comments and columns, they also offer Video and images with brief notes, which make them effective to communicate with their audiences. Afterwards, several suggestions as to how the organization's website could be improved was made. A favourable image or perception in the minds of potential clients can be created by updating the website to include additional information and various other elements. The ultimate objective is to convert potential students into actual students.

According to the results Students are not satisfied with how their current college website uses infographics, which suggests that more infographics makes it simple for them to get the information they need. It has favourable impacts on student satisfaction it increases the interactive effects in their academic enrolment, it is also vital to encourage them to use in their educational process.

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